

A Solution to Network Protocol Issues for Directional Ad-Hoc Networks through Topology Control and a Multiple-Radio-Per-Node Architecture

Christopher Cirullo, Randall Olsen, Christopher Meagher, Robert Ferro, Joonyoung Yu, Nathaniel Stevens
Tactical Edge Wireless Networks
SSC-Pacific
San Diego, California

Abstract— Line of Sight (LOS) communications and mobile networking are important capabilities for future military operations. Central to this idea is the desire for increased bandwidth and the ability to operate in the absence of satellite-based communications. A key concept in tactical edge wireless networks and airborne backhaul networks is the use of directional antennas to boost the performance of radio systems. As most current radio and wireless networking protocols were designed for omni-directional and/or fixed infrastructure environments, the use of directional antennas introduces disrupting side effects in many protocol layers of a networking system. Solving these issues is the topic of much current academic research. In this paper we describe a Multiple-Radio-per-node Architecture (MRA) that eliminates most of these problems. That is, our solution involves making changes to the architecture of a wireless node as an alternative to making changes to the design of network protocol layers. As a result, our architecture makes it possible to immediately build fully directional mobile ad-hoc networks (MANETs) using a wide range of radios without requiring major modification to the radio or existing protocols. Instead, the focus is on building a system of controllers that understand the capabilities of a given radio and implement appropriate discovery, tracking, and topology control algorithms.

Keywords—MANET; directional antenna; phased array; media access control; routing; topology control; line of sight networks

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

It is well known that the use of high gain electronically-steerable directional antennas enhances the performance of wireless networks. The benefits include longer range, higher data rates, spatial reuse, low probability of interception and detection (LPI/LPD), and anti-jam capabilities. However, the use of such antennas in dynamic mobile environments introduces numerous problems at many layers of the network protocol stack. Standard network protocols and algorithms such as neighbor discovery, Media Access Control (MAC), routing and Quality of Service (QoS) that have been optimized for wired, omni directional and/or fixed terrestrial networks do not consider the additional degree of freedom/search space of using directional antennas. Uncoordinated beam steering disrupts the standard functions of these surrounding protocol

layers and therefore produces unstable and substantially-less-than-optimally performing networks.

Prior work has suggested that new protocols and algorithms need to be developed to effectively use directional antennas in a mobile environment. The challenge of designing new protocols is tremendous. The core issue is time synchronization between the beam pointing of a directional antenna and the functions of the surrounding network layers. New dependencies surface as the various protocols must also work together and not just independently try to adapt to directionality. Often, resolving a problem in one layer of the protocol stack introduces new complications in another. Cross-layer design is helpful to open up channels of communication between the layers so that they may cooperate, but this comes at the cost of additional complexity and increased coupling [1]. Furthermore, until there is a standard set of directional wireless protocols available for these problems, all solutions will be highly proprietary and experimental, a fact that works against our desire for antenna systems to be radio agnostic and take advantage of (not be left behind by) the continual improvements in military and commercial network radio technology.

One of the points of this paper is to highlight some of the difficult problems/issues that surface when using electronically-steerable directional antennas in highly mobile, multi-path environments. In each section we will discuss specific issues that occur at a particular network protocol layer, or system function. We will discuss MAC, routing, QoS, neighbor discovery, and tracking. All of these components are required in a deployable system and as stated earlier they must work together to achieve high performance. Other papers describe these problems in more detail and propose new or modified protocol solutions. The shortcoming of most prior research is that they tend to focus too narrowly on a specific aspect of the directional antenna problem, ignoring the effect that their solutions have on the other layers and often ignoring some of the functional real world requirements needed by a deployable system. It is also highly unlikely that in the near term, any standardized protocols supporting directional antennas will be available in commercial products that are useful to the military.

The work presented here was funded by Dr. Cynthia Dion-Schwarz, Director of Information Systems & Cyber Security in the Research Directorate, Office of the Director, Defense Research and Engineering (DDR&E).

In the context of these problems we describe how the properties of the MRA eliminate the need for new/modified protocols. As a result, our architecture makes it possible to return to the wisdom of the OSI model and immediately build fully directional MANETs using a wide range of military or low cost commercial radios that are currently available in the market. This approach directly supports the tenets of the Airborne Network Architecture as specified by the USAF Airborne Network Special Interest Group described in [2]. Furthermore, the MRA delivers significant performance improvement in terms of reduced latency and increased total network throughput.

The specifications that this paper works toward are that a directional MANET must:

- Be fully directional and not employ an “omni” antenna for any function. Use of omni antennas negates many of the positive benefits of directionality and also introduces problems such as hidden terminal issues due to asymmetries in gain.
- Not rely on GPS for timing or position information as line of sight networks are expected to work in a satellite degraded environment.
- Support neighbor discovery and tracking in a mobile environment.

II. INTRODUCTION TO THE MULTIPLE-RADIO-PER-NODE ARCHITECTURE

The Multiple-Radio-per-node Architecture (MRA) was first introduced in [3]. A single node in the MRA has multiple radios, each tied to a dedicated directional antenna and embedded controller. Such a radio-antenna pair is called a “sector.” The sector/antenna controller is what puts the smarts into “Smart Antennas”. It is a software module that understands the properties of the directional antenna and is capable of steering its beams. Likewise it also understands the capabilities of the radio and knows how to control it. By steering beams and receiving feedback from the radio at each beam position, the sector controller is able to acquire basic information such as link state and received signal strength indicator (RSSI) for various beam positions. This forms the basis for neighbor discovery, RF tracking, and topology control algorithms.

Multiple sectors are connected to a central “Master Controller” which collects link state information from all the sectors and makes topology control decisions about which links a sector should manage. The master controller at each node communicates with its peer master controllers to make distributed topology control decisions. Each radio/sector is only required to support communication in a single direction at a time (more on this later). Using this framework, many different types of radios may be used. To do this, a software module must be programmed to control the radio in an automated fashion through the radio’s provided interface. A generic software interface has been defined which facilitates migration to new radios. The better the control interface a

radio provides, the easier it will be to use. Experience shows that nearly all radios provide the basic required feedback which is link state and RSSI in a more or less timely manner. In this way, a MRA network can be truly radio agnostic.

Figure 1. Example of a Multi-Radio node with four Directional Ad-Hoc Network Technology (DANTE) Antennas [4].

III. CORE MAC LAYER ISSUES

By far, the greatest challenge to building directional networks is the disruption that beam steering causes in the MAC layer. The functions of the MAC layer, which occur on very short timescales (microseconds to a few milliseconds) must be synchronized with the beam steering of the antenna or risk not completing their cycles. Since the performance of a wireless networking system depends on efficiency at the MAC layer, it is critical to get this right. We will use the standard 802.11 protocol to illustrate our point [IEEE 802.11a-1999]. From this standard, each transmitted wireless packet receives an acknowledgement. If an acknowledgement is not received, the sending node will continue to retransmit the same frame until some retransmit threshold is passed at which point it will send a delivery failure notification up the stack. Too many failure notifications will disturb the performance tuning parameters of higher protocol layers. Uncoordinated beam steering introduces race conditions. If a node transmits a frame and either the transmitting or receiving antenna steers away before the acknowledgement arrives, the sending node will continue to retransmit unaware that an antenna is pointing in the wrong direction. Many solutions for directional MACs have been proposed to resolve these issues [5-13].

As described next, academic work on directional MACs typically fall into two main categories: A) directional MACs that try to follow a carrier sense multiple access collision avoidance (CSMA/CA) mechanism and B) directional MACs that follow a time division multiple access (TDMA) scheme.

A. CSMA/CA Type Directional MACs

CSMA/CA type MACs are contention based. All nodes must sense the channel for availability before transmitting. An issue that arises in all contention based wireless MACs is the

well known hidden node problem. The 802.11 standard describes an “omni” based Request to Send/Clear to Send (RTS/CTS) mechanism which is designed to resolve this problem. This mechanism utilizes a four way handshake for each data packet: RTS/CTS followed by a Data packet and then an acknowledgement (Ack). A transmitting node will pre-calculate the time required to complete this entire four step sequence. RTS/CTS frames contain this pre-calculated time field. Any nodes in the contention area that receive RTS or CTS frames use this calculated time field to update its network allocation vector (NAV). The NAV acts as a timer and a node may not transmit until it counts down to zero. This is known as virtual carrier sensing and is a mechanism for a transmitting node to reserve the channel for specified time duration.

Of course, directionality not only disrupts this mechanism, it produces a higher number of occurrences of the hidden terminal problem and also introduces the issue of deafness. Most CSMA/CA type directional MACs seek to borrow from the 802.11 standard and modify the RTS/CTS mechanism to consider directionality. The most common approach is to use a circular transmission for control packets such as RTS or CTS. A circular transmission is accomplished by sending the same copy of a packet out each of the k number of beams its antenna can steer. This results in obvious inefficiencies as the radio must transmit k duplicate RTS packets for every data packet. Also, when a circular CTS transmission is employed additional performance penalty is incurred. References [5-13] all describe directional MACs with differing techniques that are based on manipulation of the NAV and circular transmission of control packets. Since deafness occurs because a directional node cannot listen in all directions at the same time, the most difficult issue for CSMA/CA type directional MACs is how to sense the channel for availability in all directions using purely directional receive. Most, if not all, of the papers in the literature rely on “omni” antennas for this function which can significantly undermine the high performance potential of using high gain antennas.

In Summary, CSMA/CA type directional MACs using purely directional antennas are very complicated. They work on short time scales and require a large amount of coordination between nodes to achieve good performance. With directional antennas, the transmitter and receiver must point at each other for the duration of the transmission cycle. As the number of nodes in a network grows, the issue of which node transmits to which node in which time frame becomes increasingly more complex. Sensing the channel for availability using a purely directional receive is a problem that hasn't been satisfactorily resolved.

B. TDMA Type Directional MACs

TDMA type MACs lend themselves more naturally to using directional antennas as the issues of when and in what direction to transmit/receive are more easily coupled to the TDMA schedule. However, TDMA schedules for self forming, self healing ad-hoc networks are non-trivial. Building an efficient schedule requires knowing something about the overall topology and network data flows. For example, how does one effectively push QoS information into a TDMA MAC? Complexity increases as more nodes are added to the network.

Overall performance suffers as nodes may not simultaneously transmit in multiple directions and must wait for their timeslot. Latency times across multiple hops are greatly extended.

As noted, the design of directional MACs is quite complicated. The difficult issues of tracking and neighbor discovery persist. Increased latency and jitter will affect protocols through the application layer. Routing protocols that utilize broadcast for discovering neighbors and exchanging routes will suffer. The changing physical layer of directional antennas causes disruptions all the way up the protocol stack. Resolving these problems by making changes to a specific protocol layer is too narrowly focused and therefore highly problematic.

However, it is of note that TDMA MACs for infrastructure networks are much easier to design since there is one advantaged node (Base Station) in charge of the TDMA schedule. The majority of the logic and synchronization takes place in this one advantaged node which requires no prior coordination with any other node in the network. An example of such a system is under design with the DANTE phased array and the RT1944/U (a.k.a SeaLancet) radio. The drawback of this approach is that it cannot form a MANET and therefore is not of further interest in this paper.

IV. MULTI-RADIO ARCHITECTURE TO THE RESCUE

We now look at how the MRA is able to by-pass MAC layer problems typically associated with directional antennas. The basic concept of the MRA is rather simple and involves building networks out of “dedicated” point to point links. The term “dedicated” is used to describe links that are maintained on the timescale of seconds to minutes. This avoids the problems of trying to work at the micro- to millisecond time scales of MACs and is compatible with node mobility patterns and routing update timescales. Consider a link between two radios with directional antennas that are pointing directly at each other 100% of the time. From the radio's point of view it is as if they are both using omni antennas that are within range of each other. No ill effects at the MAC layer are observed. Real life demonstrations have proven that such a link can be maintained with high reliability in a multi-path mobile environment [3]. Reference [3] discusses techniques for maintaining links and RF-only tracking. Each MRA node employs multiple radios each with its own antenna. So, as two MRA nodes come in range they will each dedicate one of their radios to a link with the other node. From that point forward the dedicated sectors will focus on tracking and maintaining the health of that link. Since each MRA node has multiple radios, it will have other sectors available to discover and create dedicated links with other nodes. In this fashion topologies are created out of dedicated links.

Figure 2. An illustration of how networks may be formed as a collection of “dedicated” point-to-point links.

The simplicity of this design is quite powerful. The focus moves away from the challenging problem of protocol modification and on to the creation and maintenance of stable links. Topology management becomes the glue that holds the network together and current MAC, routing, and QoS protocols may be used effectively. That is not to say that there are no challenges remaining for wireless directional networks using this architecture. Mobility has an unavoidable affect on link management and topology control. Link maintenance, or “tracking,” without the aid of GPS is a difficult problem that exists in all MANETs. This problem becomes more complex when you try to solve it at the MAC layer. The MRA approach allows us to focus on this problem to better maintain stable links. Network protocols still must be able to adapt to changing topologies, however, maintaining stable dedicated links is much less disruptive than the chaos observed when each node points its beams in different directions over short (sub-second) time scales and surrounding protocol layers that are unaware of this try to adapt to the physical layer changes.

Standard use cases that we consider are ship-to-ship, ship-to-shore, ship-to-air and air-to-air communications. The distances and velocities between nodes are such that angular rates between them are typically slow and dominated by the local rotation of each node. In this approach, neighbor discovery, tracking capabilities and topology control take center stage. In the DANTE system we have demonstrated purely RF based tracking and topology control that supports local rotational rates of greater than 1500 degrees per minute. This rate of RF tracking is more than sufficient to support ship movements and aircraft maneuvers.

V. MRA PERFORMANCE BENEFITS

The MRA delivers many performance benefits such as reduced latency and greater total network throughput as a result of using multiple radios. These benefits stem from the fact that multiple radios allow a node to transmit/receive concurrently in different directions. To eliminate possible interference, one will typically set co-linear radio links to different frequencies

as shown in Figure 3. By transmitting and receiving concurrently, no delays are required to mediate channel access and a steady stream of packets may be sent across multiple hops.

T1: A transmits to B
T2: B transmits to C, AND A transmits to B
T3 C transmits to d, AND B transmits to C, AND A transmits to B

Figure 3. An example of how MRA minimizes latency and maximizes total network throughput in a multi-hop relay network.

VI. TOPOLOGY CONTROL

With multiple radios per node, an MRA network will have potential for multiple links between nodes. Selecting the correct set of links to form and the frequencies to set them on is the major focus of our current research. Figure 4 shows an example of the set of potential candidate links that are available. As nodes move around and geometries change, the set of candidate links available will also change and topologies will need to be adjusted. There is a design decision to make concerning the correct number of sectors to place on an MRA node. Yao’s lemma shows that six sectors each covering 60 degrees will always result in a fully connected graph [14]. We have developed MATLAB simulations which show that randomly placed 4 sector nodes equipped with DANTE antennas will result in a connected graph in greater than 97% of all movement patterns. The flexibility of the MRA allows us to place any number of sectors in a node. There are tradeoffs to consider and the choice of how many sectors to use and where to place them depends on the characteristics of the platform and the function of the node in the network. Different scenarios and requirements will influence this decision. Using more sectors will result in greater flexibility for topology management and higher performance.

Figure 4. Figure 4. An example of link selection choices that need to be made. Blue links represent the selected “dedicated” links out of all potential candidate links.

The papers [15-21] all discuss topology control issues for directional MANETs and offer advanced solutions. Most of these papers assume a functioning directional MAC layer which is now possible with the MRA. Future research on topology control is encouraged to work toward creating optimal topologies based on properties of the MRA.

VII. SUMMARY

Use of directional antennas provides powerful capabilities for wireless networks. However, if not properly managed, directionality and mobility create complex problems that are visible at many layers of the network protocol stack. Designing new protocols and algorithms is a challenging approach for which there are no currently available standard solutions. The Multiple-Radio-per-node Architecture eliminates most of the problems caused by directionality and thus provides an alternative to developing new protocols. The MRA is radio agnostic and we can immediately build fully directional MANETs using currently available military and commercial radios. Most importantly, the MRA provides significant network performance benefits.

References

- [1] M. Zorzi, J. Ziedler, A. Lee Swindlehurst, M. Jensen, S. Krishnamurthy, B. Rao, J. Proakis "Cross-layer issues in MAC protocol design for MIMO ad hoc networks".
- [2] HQ ESC/N11, "Airborne Network Architecture," 7 October 2004. Available: http://herbb.hanscom.af.mil/Hot_Buttons/Airborne_Networking/AN_Architecture_7_Oct_2004.doc
- [3] C. Meagher, R. Olsen, C. Meagher, R. Ferro, P. Crescini, L. Majure, "Network Solutions for Employing COTS Radios in Multi-Sector Directional Architectures," Military Communications Conference, 2008. MILCOM 2008. IEEE, vol., no., Nov. 2008.
- [4] C. Meagher, R. Olsen, C. Cirullo, R. Ferro, N. Stevens, J. Yu, "Directional Ad Hoc Networking Technology (DANTE) Performance at Sea," unpublished.
- [5] T. Korakis, G. Jakllari, L. Tassiulas, "A MAC protocol for full exploitation of Directional Antennas in Ad-Hoc Wireless Networks", ACM MobiHoc, 2003, pp98—107.
- [6] Y.B. Ko, V. Shankarkumar, and N.H. Vaidya, "Medium access control protocols using directional antennas in ad hoc networks", In Proceedings of IEEE Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM), volume 1(3), pages 13-21, Tel Aviv, Israel, Mar. 26-30 2000.
- [7] A. Nasipuri, S. Ye, J. You, R.E. Hiromoto, "A MAC protocol for mobile ad-hoc networks using directional antennas", In Proceedings of IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), Chicago, IL, Sep. 23-28 2000.
- [8] R. Ramanathan, "On the performance of Ad Hoc Networks with Beamforming Antennas", ACM MobiHoc, October 2001.
- [9] M. Takai, J. Martin, A. Ren, R. Bagrodia "Directional Virtual Carrier Sensing for Directional Antennas in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks", ACM MobiHoc, June 2002.
- [10] M. Sanchez, T. Giles, J. Zander, "CSMA/CA with Beam Forming Antennas in Multi-Hop Packet Radio," In proceedings of the Swedish Workshop on Wireless Ad-Hoc Networks, March 2001.
- [11] R.R. Choudhury, X. Yang, R. Ramanathan, N.H. Vaidya "Using Directional Antennas for Medium Access Control in Ad Hoc Networks", ACM MobiCom, Sept. 2002.
- [12] J. Zander, "Slotted ALOHA multihop packet radio networks with directional antennas," Electronics Letters, vol. 26, no. 25, 1990.
- [13] Z. Zhang "DTRA: Directional Transmission and Reception Algorithms in WLANs with Directional Antennas for QoS support", IEEE Network, May/June 2005.
- [14] A. C. Yao, "On Constructing Minimum Spanning Trees in k-dimensional Spaces and Related Problems", SIAM J. Comput., 11(4): 721-736, 1982.
- [15] U. Kumar, H. Gupta, S.R. Das, "A Topology Control Approach to Using Directional Antennas in Wireless Mesh Networks", Proc. IEEE Conf. Comm (ICC 2006), 2006.
- [16] G. Pei, D. Lofquist, R. Lin, J. Erickson, "Network Topology Management for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks With Directional Links", in MILCOM 2002.
- [17] D. Van Hook, M. Yeager, J. Laird, "Automated Topology Control for Wideband Directional Links in Airborne Military Networks", in MILCOM 2005.
- [18] G. Atkinson, X. Liu, R. Nagarajan, S. Parekh, X. Jing, "Dynamic Topology Control in Ad Hoc Networks with Directional Links", in MILCOM 2005.
- [19] E. Gelal, G. Jakllari, G. S. Krishnamurthy, N. Young, "Topology Management in Directional Antenna-Equipped Ad Hoc Networks", IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, 8(5), pp. 590-605, 2009.
- [20] Thomas J. Vitolo, Jian-Qiang Hu, Leslie Servi, Vineet Mehta, "Topology Formulation For Wireless Networks With Reconfigurable Directional Links", in MILCOM 2005.
- [21] G. Hadynski, S.B. Lee, G. Rajappan, R. Sundaram, X. Wang, F. Zhou, "Optimization of Directional Antenna Network Topology in Airborne Networks", in MILCOM 2010.